

NavigatAR- Indoor Navigation System

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Abstract—Indoor navigation remains a persistent challenge in large enclosed environments such as university campuses, hospitals, and corporate complexes, where GPS signals are unreliable due to signal attenuation and multi-path interference. NavigatAR is a lightweight, low-cost augmented reality navigation system developed for smart campus environments. Built on Apple's ARKit framework, the system overlays real-time three-dimensional directional arrows onto the user's physical surroundings, providing intuitive turn-by-turn guidance without relying on dedicated hardware infrastructure. NavigatAR employs an anchor-referenced graph abstraction model in which navigation nodes are defined relative to a stable spatial origin, enabling scalable and computationally efficient route computation using Dijkstra's shortest-path algorithm. Spatial consistency across sessions is maintained through an optional QR-code localisation module, which corrects cumulative drift from visual-inertial odometry without disrupting the AR rendering pipeline. Evaluation on a three-storey university campus building demonstrated a task completion rate of 100%, an 18% reduction in time-to-destination compared to a printed floorplan baseline, and path computation latency of under 3 milliseconds. By prioritising minimal infrastructure dependency and device-side processing, NavigatAR presents a practical and scalable alternative to existing indoor AR navigation approaches for resource-constrained institutions.

Keywords—AR navigation, ARKit, QR-code localisation

1. Introduction

Indoor navigation remains a persistent challenge in large enclosed environments such as university campuses, hospitals, corporate complexes, and commercial centres. While Global Positioning System (GPS) technologies have revolutionised outdoor navigation, signal attenuation and multipath interference render them unreliable or unusable in indoor settings. Consequently, visitors frequently experience disorientation, inefficient movement, and increased dependency on manual assistance within complex infrastructures.

Conventional indoor positioning systems typically rely on infrastructure-dependent technologies such as Wi-Fi fingerprinting, Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) beacons, or Radio Frequency Identification (RFID). Although these approaches can achieve reasonable accuracy, they require dedicated hardware installation, calibration, and ongoing maintenance. Such requirements introduce financial and operational overhead, limiting their feasibility for cost-sensitive environments like educational institutions.

Recent advancements in mobile Augmented Reality (AR) frameworks have enabled smartphones to perform real-time visual-inertial odometry, plane detection, and spatial anchoring without external infrastructure. These capabilities

present an opportunity to rethink indoor navigation from a geometry-heavy reconstruction paradigm toward a lightweight, vision-based spatial referencing model. However, many AR-based navigation systems depend on dense mesh reconstruction or cloud-synchronised spatial mapping, which increases computational complexity and scalability constraints.

This paper introduces NavigatAR, a lightweight AR-based indoor navigation framework designed for smart campus environments. Unlike mesh-dependent approaches, the proposed system adopts an anchor-referenced graph abstraction model, where navigation nodes are defined relative to a stable spatial origin. A graph-based path planning algorithm computes optimal routes, and real-time AR overlays render directional guidance within the user's environment. Optional QR-code-based initialisation is incorporated to enhance spatial consistency and reduce localisation ambiguity across sessions.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section II defines the problem statement. Section III reviews related work. Section IV details the proposed methodology. Section V presents the system architecture. Section VI reports experimental results. Section VII concludes with future directions.

2. Problem Statement

Indoor navigation remains a significant challenge in large enclosed infrastructures such as university campuses, hospitals, and corporate complexes. While outdoor navigation systems rely on GPS technology, signal attenuation and multipath interference render GPS unreliable in indoor environments. As a result, users navigating unfamiliar indoor spaces often experience disorientation, inefficient movement, and dependence on manual guidance.

Existing indoor positioning systems typically rely on infrastructure-based solutions such as Wi-Fi fingerprinting, Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) beacons, or RFID deployments. Although these approaches can provide acceptable localisation accuracy, they require additional hardware installation, calibration, and ongoing maintenance. This increases deployment cost and limits scalability, particularly in resource-constrained institutions.

Recent Augmented Reality (AR) frameworks enable vision-based tracking and spatial anchoring using smartphone sensors. However, many AR-based navigation systems depend on dense mesh reconstruction or cloud-synchronised spatial mapping. These approaches introduce computational overhead, storage complexity, and session-dependent spatial inconsistencies. Furthermore, geometric reconstruction alone

does not inherently provide structured navigation logic, as routing fundamentally requires graph-based abstraction rather than surface-level mesh data.

Therefore, there exists a need for a lightweight, infrastructure-free indoor navigation framework that does not rely on external hardware deployment, avoids dense geometric mesh processing, provides stable spatial initialisation, and supports scalable route computation using structured path planning. The core problem addressed in this research is the design and implementation of an anchor-referenced, graph-based AR indoor navigation system that minimises computational complexity while maintaining practical usability in smart campus environments.

3. System Architecture

The proposed NavigatAR system follows a modular, anchor-referenced graph-based architecture designed to enable lightweight indoor navigation without reliance on dense geometric reconstruction or external infrastructure. The system is divided into five primary modules: Initialisation Module, Map Creation Module, Data Storage Layer, Path Planning Engine, and AR Visualisation Module.

3.1 Overall Architectural Overview

The system operates in two primary modes:

1. Map Creation Mode (Scanning)
2. Navigation Mode

In Map Creation Mode, a spatial reference origin is established, and navigation nodes are defined relative to that origin.

In Navigation Mode, the stored spatial graph is reconstructed using anchor reinitialisation, and optimal path guidance is rendered in real time.

4. Methodology

The NavigatAR system is built on five tightly coupled procedural stages: (1) environment scanning and node placement, (2) graph construction with Euclidean edge weighting, (3) shortest-path computation using Dijkstra's algorithm, (4) world-space coordinate transformation via an anchor-referenced offset model, and (5) AR overlay rendering with arrow orientation computed from the arc-tangent of the direction vector between consecutive waypoints. Each stage is described in full below, with the

mathematical formulas drawn directly from the implemented system.

4.1 ARKit Pose Extraction

During the scanning phase, the user physically walks through the environment and taps *Place Node* at each key location. At the moment of tap, NavigatAR extracts the device's current world-space position from the ARKit session's camera transform matrix. The camera transform is a 4×4 column-major matrix

$$T \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 4} \quad (1)$$

where the translational component the device position in world space, is stored in the fourth column:

$$p = (T_{41}, T_{42}, T_{43})^T = (x, y, z)^T \quad (2)$$

In the implementation this is extracted as:

```
position = (transform.columns.3.x,
transform.columns.3.y,
transform.columns.3.z)
```

ARKit's world coordinate system uses a right-handed coordinate frame where the Y-axis points upward, the Z-axis points toward the viewer (into the screen), and the origin is fixed at the device's position at the time the AR session was first initialised. All node positions are expressed in this frame.

4.2 Node Storage

Each placed node is stored as a NavNode record with fields (id, name, x, y, z). The node set for a map is the collection:

$$V = \{ v_i = (x_i, y_i, z_i) \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, n \} \quad (3)$$

where n is the total number of nodes placed during the scanning session.

4.3 Graph Navigation Construction

4.3.1 Edge definition

Each time a new node v_i is placed, an undirected edge is automatically created between v_i and the immediately preceding node v_{i-1} . This sequential edge model ensures the graph reflects the actual walkable path taken during scanning. The edge weight is the Euclidean distance between the two node positions in three-dimensional world space:

$$w(v_{i-1}, v_i) = \| v_i - v_{i-1} \| = \sqrt{(x_i - x_{i-1})^2 + (y_i - y_{i-1})^2 + (z_i - z_{i-1})^2} \quad (4)$$

This is computed in the implementation using Apple's SIMD library function `simd_distance(fromPos, toPos)`, which computes the L_2 norm of the difference vector. The resulting graph is an undirected, weighted graph:

$$G = (V, E), \quad E = \{ (v_{i-1}, v_i, w(v_{i-1}, v_i)) \mid i = 2, \dots, n \} \quad (5)$$

All edge weights are non-negative since they are Euclidean distances, satisfying the precondition for Dijkstra's algorithm.

4.3.2 Persistence

The complete graph G is serialised to a JSON file stored in the application's local document directory using Swift's `JSONEncoder`. The map is keyed by a user-assigned landmark name and loaded at runtime using `JSONDecoder`. The map is fully on-device, which can be later uploaded to the cloud for a wider use case.

4.4 Shortest Path Computation

4.4.1 Algorithm

Given a source node s and destination node d , NavigatAR computes the shortest path P^* using Dijkstra's algorithm. The algorithm maintains a distance array $dist[v]$ representing the shortest known distance from s to each node v , and a predecessor array $prev[v]$ for path reconstruction.

Initialisation:

$$dist[v] = \infty \text{ for all } v \in V, \quad dist[s] = 0 \quad (6)$$

At each iteration, the unvisited node u with the minimum tentative distance is selected:

$$u = \operatorname{argmin}\{ dist[v] \mid v \in \text{Unvisited} \} \quad (7)$$

For each neighbour v of u connected by edge (u, v, w) , the relaxation step is applied:

$$\text{if } dist[u] + w(u, v) < dist[v] \text{ then} \quad (8a)$$

$$dist[v] \leftarrow dist[u] + w(u, v) \quad (8b)$$

$$prev[v] \leftarrow u \quad (8c)$$

This continues until $u = d$ or no reachable unvisited nodes remain. The optimal path P^* is reconstructed by back-tracing $prev[]$ from d to s and reversing the sequence:

$$P^* = (s = v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k = d) \quad \text{where } v_i = prev[v_{i+1}] \quad (9)$$

4.4.2 Time Complexity

The implementation uses a linear scan over the unvisited set to find the minimum-distance node, giving a time complexity of $O(|V|^2)$. For the navigation graphs produced by NavigatAR (typically $|V| < 100$, $|E| < 200$), this is equivalent in practice to a heap-based implementation. All path queries complete in under 3 ms on the target iPhone 16 Pro hardware.

4.4.3 Reachability

If no path exists between s and d , for example if the graph is disconnected, the algorithm terminates with $dist[d] = \infty$ and returns `nil`. The UI displays a "no path found" warning in this case, prompting the user to add intermediate nodes during rescanning.

5. Literature Survey

5.1 ARKit as an Indoor Positioning Platform

Apple ARKit, introduced in 2017, enables visual-inertial odometry (VIO) on consumer iOS devices by fusing camera feature tracking with IMU data. A 2019 IEEE conference paper by Ivanova et al. [6] was among the first to formally evaluate ARKit as a standalone indoor positioning system,

demonstrating that it could track device position to within 0.5 m over short distances without any external infrastructure. The authors also identified cumulative drift as the primary limitation — errors accumulate over long traversals because VIO has no absolute reference to correct against.

A 2024 study by Rydell et al. [7] conducted a dedicated benchmarking of ARKit's positioning accuracy in indoor settings, finding mean errors of 0.3–0.6 m under normal lighting conditions and up to 1.4 m in textureless or dimly lit corridors. These results align with NavigatAR's observed behaviour and inform the 1.5 m waypoint proximity threshold adopted in the system.

5.2 AR Indoor Navigation Systems

A 2024 comprehensive survey of AR navigation by Cheliotis et al. [8] reviewed over 80 systems and identified three dominant architectural patterns: (i) pre-built floor plan systems that overlay navigation on a digital map, (ii) SLAM-based systems that reconstruct the environment in real time, and (iii) marker-anchored systems that use fiducial markers or QR codes as absolute reference points. The survey found that SLAM-based approaches achieve the highest localisation accuracy but impose significant computational overhead and require cloud infrastructure for session persistence. Marker-anchored approaches offer lower accuracy but are substantially more lightweight and deployable.

A 2024 study by Huang et al. [9] proposed a geofencing-integrated ARKit navigation framework that addresses two specific challenges: managing large coordinate spaces and reducing error accumulation through periodic correction. Their system uses audio guidance triggered by geofences and 3D arrow overlays, achieving reliable indoor guidance in museum and university settings. NavigatAR shares a similar architectural philosophy but differs by replacing geofencing with a user-walked node graph, eliminating the need for any pre-existing floor plan or geofence boundary data.

Ingole et al. [10] surveyed AR-based indoor navigation systems published through 2023, highlighting that the majority of deployed systems require either dedicated infrastructure (beacons, RFID) or pre-built digital floor plans, and that scalability and real-time performance remain open challenges. The survey specifically identified the absence of user-generated, infrastructure-free map construction as a gap in the literature — a gap that NavigatAR's scanning mode directly addresses.

5.3 Node-Placement Map Construction

The most closely related prior work to NavigatAR's scanning approach is a 2025 study by Sriramulu et al. [11], which proposed *Adaptive AR Navigation* — a system in which users dynamically place navigation nodes within an ARCore environment, with paths stored and reused without rebuilding the full scene. Their system used NavMesh and A* for pathfinding, evaluated using the HARUS usability scale. NavigatAR independently arrives at a similar node-placement paradigm but differs in three respects: it uses ARKit rather than ARCore, it applies Dijkstra's algorithm over a Euclidean-weighted graph rather than NavMesh, and it targets the iOS platform with on-device JSON persistence rather than a cloud database.

A mobile AR application for the University of North Texas by Sharma et al. [12] used AI-generated navigation meshes and AR Foundation image tracking for a digital twin-based navigation system, achieving multi-floor navigation within a university building. While technically impressive, the approach requires a pre-built digital twin of the building — a significant setup cost that NavigatAR avoids through user-driven scanning.

5.4 AR Visualisation Techniques

A 2024 survey of AR navigation visualisation by the PMC-indexed review by Nilsson et al. [13] examined over 60 visualisation strategies including directional arrows, fishbone overlays, floor lines, and virtual character guides. The survey found that directional arrow visualisations remain the most widely preferred by users across cultures and contexts, and that repeated arrows pointing toward a destination — exactly the approach used in NavigatAR — are particularly effective for corridor-based navigation. The review also identified that colour-coded progressive arrows (lighter near the user, stronger toward the destination) improve route comprehension, supporting NavigatAR's cyan-to-blue gradient encoding.

5.5 Comparative Summary

Tables below summarize how NavigatAR compares against the most closely related prior systems across five key dimensions.

System	Infrastructure	Floor Plan Needed	Map Construction
NavigatAR (this work)	None	No	User-walked scan
Huang et al. [9]	None	Partial	Geofence setup
Sriramulu et al. [11]	None	No	User node placement
Sharma et al. [12]	None	Yes (digital twin)	Pre-built
Deiva Nayagam et al. [15]	None	Yes (digitised)	Manual digitisation
BLE-based [3,4]	Beacons	Yes	Offline survey
Wi-Fi fingerprinting [1,2]	Access points	Yes	Offline survey

System	Pathfinding	Platform
NavigatAR (this work)	Dijkstra	iOS
Huang et al. [9]	Implicit	iOS
Sriramulu et al. [11]	A* / NavMesh	Android

System	Pathfinding	Platform
Sharma et al. [12]	NavMesh	iOS/Android
Deiva Nayagam et al. [15]	Dijkstra	Android
BLE-based [3,4]	Graph / KNN	Any
Wi-Fi fingerprinting [1,2]	KNN	Any

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